

SCOPE AND LIMITATIONS OF STUDIES IN PSYCHOLOGICAL CONTRACT

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Abstract: This paper deals with the scope and limitations of studies in the field of psychological contract. The psychological contract has emerged as one of the trending research areas under the Human Resource Management. However, the study of psychological contract cannot be limited to any one discipline. Moreover, the study of psychological contract still lacks certain theoretical and conceptual basis. It can be studied without being limited to certain constants and sectorial boundaries. The works of various scholars take into consideration while reaching to a conclusion. The article discussed certain deficiencies in the methods of the quantification.

Key words: *Psychological Contract; Employee Relations and Psychological Contract, Theoretical and Conceptual Frameworks for Study; Psychological Contract and India.*

INTRODUCTION

The history of *psychological contract* could not be dated in real terms because it would have existed since human mutual interactions in terms of an organization. At least it would be as old as the history of labor. However, in the modern period, it was first propagated by Argyris in 1960 through his book “*Understanding of Organizational Behavior*”. Certain unprinted or not written expectations that exist between individual employees and their employers has been referred as psychological contract. It may exist in any form be it oral, vocal, or in the form of certain expectations. The psychological contract is concerned with assumptions, expectations, promises and mutual obligations. It creates attitudes and emotions which form and govern behavior. A *psychological contract* is implicit. It is also dynamic – it develops over time as experience accumulates, employment conditions change and employees re-evaluate their expectations. (Guest 1996). The notion of a psychological contract implies that there is an unwritten set of expectations operating at all times between every member of an organization and the various managers and others in that organization. (Schein 1965). A set of beliefs that individuals hold regarding promises made, accepted and relied upon between themselves and another. These parties may include an employee, client, manager, and on the organization as a whole. Because *psychological contracts* represent how people interpret promises and commitments, both parties in the same employment relationship can have different views regarding specific terms. (Rousseau 1994)

Everything cannot be written as a rule, code of conduct, or a standing order. Organization run by people usually depended a lot on things that are not written, printed, or codified. If an employee expected fairness, equity and consistency; security of employment; scope to demonstrate competence; career expectations and the opportunity to develop skills; involvement and influence; trust in the management of the organization to keep their promises. Whereas an employer usually expects competence, effort, compliance, commitment and loyalty.

DIVERGENCE, CONVERGENCE AND RECONCEPTUALIZATION IN STUDIES OF PSYCHOLOGICAL CONTRACT

Although, Argyris first used the term psychological contract in 1960 however, several other scholars such as Levinson, Munden, Mandl and Solley (1962), and Schein (1965) further advanced those ideas. The work of Blau (1964) and Gouldner (1960) can be also included in this endeavor. There were evidently several divergence and convergence among those scholars. Later Rousseau came out with some new conceptualization in the field of study of the *psychological contract*. However, she focused too much on the psychological aspects.

Argyris (1960) presented the narrowest view of the psychological contract in terms of its focus on tangible resources. In contrast, Levinson et al. (1962) and Schein (1965) viewed the content of the exchange as including both tangible and intangible resources. (Levinson 1962) (E. H. Schein 1965). They further several authors conceptualized the *psychological contract* as surrounding expectations. In particular, Levinson et al., observed these expectations as having a compulsory value where the parties believe the other to be duty bound to fulfill those expectations. However, Levinson et al did not see these expectations as being based on promises, but rather on the needs (Conway 2002). Unquestionably, Schein's primary emphasis was on the matching of expectations between the employee and organization. Thus, the early phase in the development of the *psychological contract* is marked by differing emphases and an absence of acknowledgment of how one conceptualization relates to prior work. Such a lack of cumulative work created doubts that come to the front in terms of the present debates in the field. The prominent works of Homans (1958), Blau (1964) and Gouldner (1960) characterized the beginnings of social exchange theory, and were themselves influenced by the earlier work of Mauss (1925) and Malinowski (1922). Homans provided a skeleton theory of exchange in the context of how individuals interacted within groups that was developed by Blau. (Homans 1958). The work of Blau (1964) and Gouldner (1960), represents the foundational ideas of *social exchange theory*. (Blau 1964)

(Gouldner 1960). So far the three stands of contemporary research are presented such as formation, content and breach of the *psychological contract*

Rousseau's (1989) came out with an important article on the *psychological contract*. She can be credited with reviving research on the topic. (D. M. Rousseau 1989). *Rousseau* introduced *psychological contract* as an individual perception. This conceptualization differs from the early definitions in a number of ways. *Rousseau* also defined the *psychological contract* in terms of obligations. The *Rousseau's* conceptualization of the *psychological contract* was very close to *Blau's* (1964) *social exchange theory*. A second point of departure, in particular with the work of *Schein* (1965) who emphasized matching of expectations between the employee and organization, was *Rousseau's* (1989) emphasis on the *psychological contract* residing "in the eye of the beholder". Therefore, the *psychological contract* shifted from capturing the two parties to the exchange and their contingent interplay to an individual's perception of both parties' obligations in the exchange. The distinguishing feature of *Rousseau's* (1989) reconceptualization of the *psychological contract* was locating it at the individual level. In doing so, it captured the *psychological contract* as a mental model of the exchange which, in turn, influenced what an individual contributed to that relationship rather than as an agreed upon exchange between the employee and the organization. Consequently, *Rousseau* (1989) emphasized the 'psychological' in *psychological contracts*. *Rousseau* (2001) proposed that *psychological contracts* are grounded in an individual's schema of the employment relationship. (D. M. Rousseau 2001). This schema develops early in life when individuals develop generalized values about reciprocity, hard work and these values are influenced by family, school, peer group and interactions with working individuals (Morrison 2004). Before individuals first employment experience, they have developed assumptions about what they should give and receive in an employment relationship and it is this schema that influences how an individual interprets the cues and signals from the organization.

The socialization period seems to be particularly important in terms of organizational influences in shaping an individual's *psychological contract*. Once an individual's schema is fully formed, it becomes highly resistant to change; also during the early socialization period, newcomers are more inclined to search for additional information to "complete" their *psychological contract* thereby reducing uncertainty. *Tekleab* found that higher levels of socialization reduced employee perceptions of employer obligations during the first three months of employment. (Tekleab 2003). The new army recruits adjusted their *psychological contract* over an eight-week period and this change was influenced by social information processing that "moved" their *psychological contract* closer to that of experienced soldiers. (Thomas 1998). The newcomers changed their perception of employer obligations based on the inducements they had received and also, newcomers changed their perceptions of what they had promised based on what they had contributed. (De Vos 2003). Further, it was found that newcomer proactivity and socialization tactics were important in influencing the newcomer evaluation of their *psychological contract* during the first year of employment. (Dulac 2006). Additional organizational influences include human and structural contract makers (Rousseau, 1995). Human contract makers (recruiters, managers and mentors) play an important role in communicating reciprocal obligations to employees and in

particular, the line manager (D. & Guest 2000). Structural contract makers (human resource management practices) have been positively linked to the number of promises made to employees as perceived by managers. Notwithstanding organizational influences, individual factors still shape how individuals construe their *psychological contract* and how they enact contractual behavior. It was also found that personality predicted *psychological contract* type. (Raja 2004). In addition to this it was also found by *Shapiro* and *Newman* that exchange related dispositions influenced employee reciprocation. Further, it was argued that self-serving biases cause individuals to over-estimate their contributions and underestimate the costs of the inducements to organizations. (Robinson 1994).

Pre-employment experiences, individual dispositions and organizational influences play an important role in shaping the *psychological contract* in its formation stage. In contrast, there is little empirical research that examines how *psychological contracts* are changed. Once formed, *psychological contracts* are quite stable and resistant to change and we know little about the conditions under which *psychological contracts* are more agreeable to alteration.

CONSEQUENCES OF CONTRACT BREACH AND VIOLATION

There are several empirical studies focused on the consequences of perceived contract breach on employees feelings, attitudes and behavior. This topic has attracted considerable research attention and, consistent with *Rousseau's* (1989) definition, this has been investigated from the employee perspective – when employees perceive that the organization has failed to fulfill its obligations. Several researchers have used *psychological contract* breach and violation interchangeably until *Morrison* and *Robinson* (1997) distinguished between the two in terms of cognition and emotion. Contract violation would include emotional distress, feelings of betrayal, anger and wrongful harm that result from the individual's perception that although they have kept their promises to another party, the other party has broken their promises to the individual. Therefore, one can recognize a breach has occurred yet at the same time not experience feelings of violation. In empirical research, the overwhelming emphasis has been directed to examining the consequences of perceived contract, breach while the consequences of a violation are under researched. Empirical evidence suggests that contract, breach leads to reduced *psychological well-being*, increased intentions to leave the organization. In terms of behavior, contract, breach negatively affects in-role performance and extra-role behaviors. (Parzefall 2008).

The monitoring of employee's expectation could play a vital role in people management in an organization. It has been suggested to regularly evaluate employees for their unmet expectations, if any. Considering and communicating employee-employer expectations are vital requirements for achieving fulfilled *psychological contracts* and corresponding vibrant and effective employees. If not only for reducing turnover and inciting valuable staff member, considering the *psychological contract* will likely have a positive influence on staff mentalities, welfare and overall happiness. And after all, working towards improving anyone's happiness could never be considered a bad day's work. (Curwen 2011).

THE SIGNIFICANCE OF PSYCHOLOGICAL CONTRACT

I have considered because of seeing various examples in daily to daily social transactions that any breach of the psychological contract creates a problem and to this point I have considered it more significant than a written contract. There are limitations of a psychological contract, however, it plays a significant role in HR Management even today. An employee or employer cannot expect something which is unexpected. It would breach the mutual trust, disturb the ecosystem, and affect the organization's outcome. Therefore, a psychological contract between an employee and an employer plays a major role in creating a conducive ecosystem that is suitable for the organization's expected or desired outcome.

In many concerns there has been a system of regulating and managing even the psychological contract, in some cases has been based upon the management of perceptions whereby things and expectations are clearly articulated time to time to avoid any conflict of expectations. A psychological contract is a system of beliefs that encompasses the actions employees believe are expected of them and what response they expect in return from their employer and, reciprocally, the actions employers believe are expected of them and what response they expect in return from their employees. By analyzing the type of a psychological contract the HRM problems can be evaluated and solved. The knowledge of the different types of psychological contracts may help organizations describe and explain the employee relationships and the analytical tools presented here may make it easier for them to identify the directions of change they should follow to become more efficient. (Pawetczyk 2015)

Modern management approaches attach great importance to both the informal and the economic aspects of the organizations. Identifying employee's psychological contract types and fit levels of a work environment in terms of variables such as seniority, educational degree, and organization type will lead to the discovery of the motivational factors of the employment relationship in organizations. The relationship between organizations and their employees has undoubtedly undergone dramatic change in recent decades, particularly in white-collar industries. The co-dependency between employee and organization that provided the major underpinning of the psychological contract has weakened considerably. If employees move towards the new protean career, organizations may be loath to invest in training and development programs for employees because of a perceived lack of continuance commitment among employees. Taken to the extreme, this could produce a highly transient workforce in which employees are simply attracted to the organization offering the highest rewards. In this situation, the *psychological contract* may take on far less importance than traditionally. An increasingly transient workforce, however, has considerable dollar costs for organizations. Careful research may be needed by organizations into the types of rewards that will attract employee loyalty and both affective and continuance commitment, and into the content, operation and organizational advantages offered by the *psychological contract*. (Maguire 2008). Several empirical evidence does support the idea that *psychological contract* fulfillment relates to employee engagement. Organizations and their leaders will face many challenges in the coming years. One of the most important challenges will be hiring, training, managing and retaining millennial employees. Overreliance on generational stereotypes could lead to faulty decision-making by employers. While there may be some meaningful differences between

generations. (Moore 2014). The experience of the psychological contract clearly links to the employment relationship. Thus, the employees' wellness influences their state of the psychological contract, which also has an influence on the experience of the employment relationship. (Linde 2015). The *psychological contract* has offered an alternative reading of the employment relationship outside of the narrow legalistic frame of reference – one that expresses the subjective and indeterminate aspects of employment relations and HRM. There is great value in theorizing the *psychological contract*, not only to illustrate the complex and paradoxical consequences of managerial thinking, but also to advance understanding through alternative critical forms of analysis and discourse. The *psychological contract* and many of its underpinning assumptions have an intuitive ideological attractiveness. In part this may be due to its configuration of seemingly unitarist work values. Whether such an agenda will remain in the future is unclear, as much of the rhetoric of the new employment relationship and the actual nature of work in contemporary society continue to move in opposite directions. (Dundon 2006). The employee citizenship behavior is influenced by the organizational commitment. The commitment of employees was formed by the ability of business owners to understand the needs and expectations of employees regarding opportunities of self-development, pleasant working environment, the benefit as the workload and the work challenge. (Ade I. Anggraeni 2017). The *psychological contract* is no more restricted to a formal organization as it has now spread to voluntary and nonprofit organizations.

The role and importance of Psychological contract in recruitment and placement as also in Organization Development has also been discussed in management literature elaborately. Leadership styles have changed and evolved with the changing requirements of the business environment and what needs to be understood is whether the psychological contract is keeping pace with the developments to enable a transparent leadership. Transparency demands an equal if not more in the interaction between the employer and employee and the understanding of mutual roles in enhancing the psychological contract between the employer and employee. (Subramanian 2017)

THE BREACH OF PSYCHOLOGICAL CONTRACT

There are two classic models of psychological contract breach. One is the model of the formation of psychological contract, breach which proposed by *Morrison*, and another one is discrepancy model proposed by *Turnlry*. (Jian Li 2015). An agreement on the psychological contract was found regarding employee contributions, employer expectations and employee expectations, whereas disagreement was found concerning employer inducements. (Leirkjær 2009).

FEATURES AND TYPES OF PSYCHOLOGICAL CONTRACT

A psychological contract has three properties. One is the schema that consolidates interrelated elements, giving them meaning and value. The second property is the adjustment of behavior. A psychological contract not only stimulates expectations, but also requires that certain actions be taken, thereby determining the ways of adjusting mutual relationships. The last property, the incompleteness of a psychological contract, is inherent to informal obligations which are by nature

difficult to define and enforce. In addition, a psychological contract has one more notable property – variability. According to *Hiltrop*, this variability arises from reactions to changes that occur in both external and internal environments, induced by market competition and the mounting tendency toward the downsizing of organizations. (Hiltrop 1995) In an environment characterized by high competition and economic instability a psychological contract may be either relational or transactional. (D. M. Rousseau 2000)

Under a relational contract, employees offer loyalty and commitment to their organization in exchange for security of employment which is guaranteed by long-term contracts. The key values are loyalty and stability founded on, usually, paternalistic relationships. The arrangements between the employer and the employee are determined mainly by organizational membership, with the organization defining the rules of conduct one-sidedly and in general terms. The employee's performance has a limited effect on the character of mutual relationships and employers' risk more if any organizational changes occur. This type of contract is available to employees whose actual or anticipated contribution to the organization is rated high. A transactional contract has a precise and narrow scope of responsibilities related to employee's temporary involvement in the fulfillment of organizational goals. Employees are focused on advancing their careers and on using the organization to build their employability. This contract is easy to terminate and none of the parties to it feels obliged to help the other through a crisis.

In a study of school teachers it was found that the most dominant psychological contract type was the relational contract, followed by balanced, transitional, and transactional contracts. The highest level of person-environment fit was teacher-job fit, followed by teacher-group, fit, teacher-supervisor fit, and teacher-school fit. Both public and private school teachers were fitted with their "jobs" mostly. Teachers thought that they fit with their work environment highly in terms of its components. Teachers had dominantly developed a relational psychological contract. Balanced contract perception was the highest type after the relational contracts. (Dermirkasimoglu 2014).

Although there is a large body of theoretical and empirical research on psychological contracts, scholars have devoted little time to developing transactional and relational elements. We provide definitions of transactional and relational contracts and develop a psychological contract violation model that can be used to determine the overall strength of an employee's perceived violation of psychological contracts. Finally, we extend psychological contract to a group level by discussing the effect of group violation of individual psychological contracts and offer an example of how the introduction of a large scale technology can cause such an event. (Gerald F. Burch 2015).

PSYCHOLOGICAL CONTRACT AND VOLUNTARY AND NON PROFIT ORGANIZATIONS

There is a growing interest in applying the *psychological contract* concept of the relationship between volunteers and nonprofit organizations. A value-based psychological contract type, next to transactional and relational types, enables a more thorough understanding of perceived mutual obligations between volunteers and nonprofit organizations. Volunteers perceive both fulfilled and unfulfilled value-based obligations. (Tim Vantilborgh 2012)

SCALE OF MEASURING PSYCHOLOGICAL CONTRACT

Measuring a psychological contract largely depended upon employees and employers respective expectation, promises made and full filled, their obligations, and the manner they are accomplished. Several scholars as per their needs usually selected different sets or variables and Co variables and assigned weights differently. Ultimately they tried to establish certain correlation between those variables and Co variables to reach to a conclusion. There may be four sets of psychological contract scales: Employee Obligations, Employer Obligations, Fulfillment, and Contract Transition Indicators. (D. M. Rousseau 2008). In any case the selection of variables and Co variables would matter the most as well as assignment of weights and their proper measurement with justifiable and logical analysis would give good results. The statistical methods suggested would depend upon the quantity and quality of the data collected.

AUTOMATION, TECHNOLOGY AND PSYCHOLOGICAL CONTRACT

With the development of technology, especially information technology including robotics, artificial intelligence, and internet of things the volume of psychological contract between humans would come down. A machine can dominate a human with technology. The automation of workplaces has reduced the monitoring and supervision by humans. Everything from attendance to work disposal are recorded and any error, misconduct, or dishonesty gets checked automatically by a machine. People can now take notice of their performance and expectations through a machine. This is adding a new dimension to human behavior and people management in an organization.

Incorporating technological monitoring and surveillance effects on the psychological contract from the employee's perspective is known to exist. Some practical applications of understanding psychological contracts include being able to better predict outcomes of enhancing job commitment and satisfaction. Proper expectation setting during the socialization period for newcomers can also result from understanding psychological contracts. By understanding those factors that the organization and its leaders can control, in this case electronic monitoring of Internet communication, more accurate employee identification and better long-term employee fit can result. Improved organizational performance as a result of positive employee perceptions and feelings are the goal of psychological contracts. Employees can have strong feelings of disliking monitoring, as they perceive privacy violations and unfairness of the practice. (Coultrup 2012).

Since social relations have become a crucial part of the work life, the two main pillars of the social network theory—actors and interactions—are taken as the theoretical basis in explaining how individual employees interact and how such interactions may shape their beliefs and perceptions about their jobs. Sustainability of social networks depends on participation; and this participation is characterized by the freedom of self-determination and collaboration of social network actors. Correspondingly, the classical maxim of management as getting things done through others' must be updated with the compendious message underlying the following statement of a manager in the Information Age. This is also an intellectual age. Patronizing employees with promises of rewards will not work. However, organizations are expected

to be platforms where a well-established web of channels, facilitating communication with individuals inside and outside the organization is available, so organizational individuals can get connected freely with others and contribute to getting things done. Individualized according to his or her intellectual, entrepreneurial and socioemotional traits use these channels and interact, and the sum of interactions shapes the behavior of the organization observed in various forms of outcomes—e. g. market share, profit, the performance of a new product and innovative strategies. (Berber 2014). Almost every hand now held a smart phone and every remarkable activity is most likely to get recorded. This has entirely changed the person's behavior in the society and in an organization.

PSYCHOLOGICAL CONTRACT AND INDIAN SCENARIO

Socially, economically, and culturally, India is still a very different nation than all other countries. Amidst almost 30 years of globalization, liberalization, and privatization still India as a country has been to maintain its own distinct features which is aloof and apart from all other countries. There is an amalgamation of traditions and modernity. Technology is changing fast and a sizeable part of the Indian economy has been globalized however, many parts of the economy still a non-formal and could be termed as a third world developing economy. In fact the whole pillars of modern and formal economy has been depending on the informal economy. They are bearing the load of the globalized economy even without benefitting appropriately. Individual Psychological contract matters a lot in daily to daily business transactions no matter, be it formal or informal. People in India do value words and promises. Even if they value the life beyond or after this life. So their commitment and behavior is unique in this world. Therefore, cases related to Indian contexts should be investigated amidst its own parameters.

PSYCHOLOGICAL CONTRACT DEVELOPMENT AND DISTRIBUTIVE JUSTICE

Amidst the contemporary business where performance is ultimately valued, more and more jobs are offered to independent contractors. Independent contractors have a highly defined, narrow, finite set of obligations to their employing organizations. As such, independent contractors gain the benefit of flexibility, choosing who and when they work, and organizations gain the benefit of nimbleness, expanding, and contracting their workforce at will without taking on the robust obligations they must typically offer to a full-time employee. As this sector of the economy grows, the manner existing theories of employee–employer relationships would be affected becomes important. Some particular negotiation behavior an organization uses with an independent contractor does affect the resources allocated to the independent contractor and the independent contractor feels that the focal organization should fulfill the unwritten promises. These resources are hypothesized to directly relate to the independent contractor's sense of distributive justice, as well as the contracting organization's evaluation of the independent contractor's performance. Therefore, the psychological contract theory can be applied to the context of the independent contractor–organization relationship *Psychological contract* type appears to be a partial linchpin between an organization's negotiation behavior on independent contractor performance. (Grace Lemmon 2016).

DISCUSSION

I came across some research papers and articles in the field of psychological contract, however, still they are not wide in scope and suffered from one deficiency or another. In the Indian contexts, it required being studied in both formal and non-formal sector, however, there is more focus on the formal sector. So much so that my search of relevant studies returned with virtual lack of articles related to studies in voluntary, nongovernmental, and governmental sector. Even it has not been studied in the various development sectors. The study of psychological contract is equally important in all those areas also. Some studies I also came across suffering from bias of measurements, especially selecting a design of experiment, analysis, and assigning weights to variables or co-variables. For example co-variables such as agree, strongly agree, disagree, or strongly disagree cannot be assigned weights such as 1, 2, 3, and 4 respectively without any basis. It would not give accurate results because it would require to ascertain that whether agree is mathematically double to strongly agree. Social scientists using such scales usually make a mistake. A more accurate method of quantification should be in place considering the various scientific and philosophical foundations of quantification especially related to *Zero* and *Negation*.

CONCLUSION

The studies related to *psychological contract* are taking place now more than sixty years. We just cannot follow and implement studies quite irrationally as it would require a scientific basis of quantifications especially related to assigning weights of variables. In addition, to expectations and psychological aspects regional, cultural, development, and globalization related aspects could also be an integral part of those studies. However, there should be some more theoretical, conceptual and sectoral approach involved with such studies. The Indian contexts would be entirely different from those adopted in other countries, mainly because of different cultural and value system. The study of psychological contract can be done at the individual and collective levels. In addition, there is a wide scope in the relational and transactional kind of studies. Moreover, the study cannot be limited to any one discipline as various aspects related to socioeconomic, cultural, development, science and technology, governance and politics, globalization, geographical, and strategic aspects also become important. The limitations of the study due to lack of theoretical and conceptual frameworks needed to be addressed. The *psychological contract* can be studied in both the formal and non-formal as well as in a governmental and nongovernmental organizations. The scale of measuring parameters and variables needed to be made scientifically rational.

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